

FEATURES OF THE TASK-BASED METHOD IN TEACHING PROFESSIONAL ENGLISH

Pernebayeva Akjana Erkinovna

National University of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7972729>

Abstract: The article is dedicated to the analysis of the application of the task-based method, which for a long period of time has been used for teaching the professional English language, with the aim of defining to what extent students use the material learned previously, in real situations. The author offers a direction for searching the most efficient approaches and ways of solving the question of developing the problematic active basis for teaching the professional English language. The main stages of the lesson using the task-based method are examined and analyzed. Particular attention is paid to the advantages and disadvantages of this method. As a result of the research, it was indicated that the taskbased method promotes the development of communication skills in pairs and groups, the ability of all participants to argue and debate in the learning process.

Key words: Task-based method, professional English language, language and communicative skills, work individually or in pairs, planning, analysis, practice.

In task-based learning, the lesson is mainly focused on the task itself (grammar reference and lexical area are not so important). The aim of the lesson is not to learn the structure' but to perform the task'. It's important to note that if students want to fulfill the task successfully they have to use the right language and exchange their ideas with each other. The language, however, becomes an instrument of communication which helps to complete the task correctly. To reach the objective students can use any words they know. Sometimes there is no correct answer for a task outcome. Students make their own decision how to complete it and use appropriate language.

Having analyzed the scientific research on the task-based problem, the following fact can be admitted that the stated problem was searched by the scientists at different times. Studying of the fundamental works shows that students can learn more effectively when they are actively involved in the learning process. Y. P. Surmin, D. L. Rogers, D. Brown, A.L. George, A.J. Bennett, C.Richards, Thomas S. C. Farrell, R. Benbunan-Fich, S. R. Hiltz, N. V. Akinfieva, O. V. Bobienko and others, showed the problems dealing with the task-based method implementation in the process of teaching higher school students. Ellis Rod observed that his students could just as easily learn languagethrough linguistic problems as they could with non-linguistic problems. Ellis Rod also was of the belief that tasks were a way to tap into a learner's natural mechanisms for second language acquisition. This method allows teachers and students to concentrate on how language is used to achieve understanding between persons, and how language can be used to accomplish certain tasks.

The main function of the task-based method is to teach students to solve complex unstructured problems that cannot be solved in a logical way. The method promotes the development of independent thinking among students, the ability to listen and take into account the alternative point of view, to give reasoning for their own, formulates interest and positive motivation towards learning. With the help of this method, students have the opportunity to develop and improve analytical and evaluative skills, learn to work in a team,

find the most rational solution to the problem posed and master the ability to use the material in practice.

The task-based method includes elements of research training, developmental learning, and project activities. In the process of analyzing the situation, students immerse themselves in an imaginary professional reality, explore and analyze the problem, interacting with each other, exchanging discoveries using English language.

Teachers have the alternative in teaching a foreign language while using task - based learning. In a task-based lesson the tutors don't pre-determine what language will be studied, the lesson is based around the completion of a main task and the language studied is determined by what happens as the students complete it. There is the following order of such lessons:

1. Pre-task:

The topic of the lesson is introduced by the teacher who gives the students clear instructions on what they will have to do at the task stage and might help the students to refresh some language in their minds that may be useful for the task. The students have the opportunity to think about the theme of the lesson and to express their ideas and opinions to each other and to the teacher. A variety stimulating activities may be used such as answering quiz questions, reflecting on different options and completing charts. The class may work individually or in simultaneous pairs, take notes and spend time preparing for the task. It is important to get the students to use the key expressions in the useful language box that they have. The teacher goes around, monitors and assists where necessary.

2. Task:

In this stage, the students complete the task either in pairs or small groups. It depends on the type of the activity. The instructor is generally reduced to the role of observer.

3. Planning:

Then the students practice what they are going to say in pairs or in groups in order to engage all the participants. A short oral or written report related to the issues can be presented to tell the whole class. The teacher gives each pair or group several minutes to discuss how to answer a question related to the task, and then ask a randomly selected person to present the group's answer and reasoning. During this time the teacher monitors the language being used, notes down the points than need correction, gives a piece for advice.

4. Report:

Students then report back to the class orally or read the written report. The teacher chooses the order of when students will present their reports and may give the students some quick feedback on the content. At this stage the teacher may also play a recording of others doing the same task for the students to compare.

5. Analysis:

The teacher then highlights relevant parts from the text of the recording for the students to analyze. They may ask students to notice interesting features within this text. The teacher can also highlight the language that the students used during the report phase for analysis.

6. Practice or feedback:

At the end, the teacher chooses language areas to practice based upon the needs of the students and what is emerged from the task and report phases. After that the students do practice activities to increase their confidence and focus on useful language. While preparing the task-based lesson, the teacher should pay attention to the following steps:

- to clear up learning objectives;
- to adopt the lesson to the map of the course or unit;
- to identify the best strategy for using the task-based materials;
- to take into the consideration students' level of knowledge, skills and abilities.

Work of students on the content of the task-based lessons can be assessed by the teacher in the following skills: analytical, organizational, decision-making skills, interpersonal communication skills, creativity, oral and written communication skills in a foreign language (lexicon and grammatical aspect). There are following evaluation criteria and number of points (total 100 points):

1. Lexical and grammatical skills and abilities (30 points):

- use of lexicon on the topic (10 points);
- the use of communicative clichés according to the situation (5 points);
- the use of a variety of grammatical constructions in accordance with the task and the requirements of the given year of language training (5 points);
- pronunciation (5 points);
- literacy speech (5 points);

2. Content (30 points):

- compliance with the topic, sufficient depth of disclosure of the topic (10 points);
- ability to make decisions and argue them. Ability to draw conclusions (10 points);
- ability to ask and answer questions from an opponent. Ability to argue their answers (10 points);

3. Analytical skills (20 points):

- possession of reasoning logic (10 points);
- the skill of searching, analyzing and evaluating information (10 points);

4. Organizational Skills and Skills (20 points):

- compliance with regulations (5 points);
- activity (5 points);
- ability to work in a team and make decisions (10 points).

Further to the practical application and testing of scholarly knowledge, task-based method can also help students prepare for real-world problems, situations and crises by providing an approximation of various professional environments. Thus, through the examination of specific tasks, students are given the opportunity to work out their own professional issues through the trials, experiences and research findings of others. An obvious advantage of this method is that it allows students the exposure to settings and contexts that they might not otherwise experience. This method also incorporates the idea that students can learn from one another by disputing with each other, by asserting something and then having it questioned.

References:

1. Benbunan-Fich R., Hiltz S. R. Educational Applications of CMCS: Solving Case Studies through Asynchronous Learning Networks / R. Benbunan-Fich, S.R. Hiltz. – JCMC, 1999. № 4

- (3). March 1999 [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <http://www.ascisc.org/jcmc/vol4/issue3/index.html>.
2. Brown D. Teaching by Principles: Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy. – 2-nd edition / D. Brown. Addison Wesley; Longman, 2001. 480 p.
3. Ellis Rod. Task-based Language Learning and Teaching. Oxford, New York: Oxford Applied Linguistics, 2003. 379 p.
4. George, A.L., Bennett, A. Case studies and theory development in the social sciences. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2005. 332 p.
5. Nunan David. Task Based Language Teaching. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004. 222 p.
6. Richards J. C., Farrell Thomas S. C. Professional Development for Language Teachers (Strategies for Teacher Learning) / J. C. Richards, Thomas S. C. Farrell. – Cambridge University Press, 2005. 202 p.
7. Rogers D. L. A Paradigm Shift: Technology Integration for Higher Education in the New Millennium / D. L. Rogers // Educational Technology Review. Spring/Summer, 2000. № 13. P. 19–33.
8. Akinfiyeva N.V. Strategicheskie obrazovatelnyie tehnologii: suschnost, otlichitelnyie priznaki [Strategic educational technologies: essence, distinctive features] / N. V.Akinfiyeva [Elektronnyiy resurs]. <http://www.ipk.admin.tsu.ru/resurs/katalogs/2002/kat>.
9. Bobienko O.M. Teoreticheskie podhodyi k probleme klyuchevyih kompetentsiy [Theoretical approaches to the problem of key competences] / O.M. Bobienko. [Elektronnyiy resurs]. Vestnik TISBI, 2003. <http://www.tisbi.ru/science/vestnik/2003/issue2/cult3.php/cult3.php>.